
MULTIMODALITY AND ITS RELATION TO CONSTRUCT-OBJECT THEORY

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Abstract

In this essay, I advance the semiotics of Museum Theory by explaining its relationship to multimodality and the Construct-Objects of Flynn. I propose, following Vervaeke, that the universe is inherently *transjective*; further, I assert that *epistemic mutual intelligibility* reveals a correspondence of ontologies between two agents. I focus on dipolar construct-objects, which form a unified dimension from which schemata can be constructed. Some speculation on the role of excesses and imbalances of the imitative-innovative dimension and their clinical significance is presented. A new notion of mathematical cognition, the *perceptomorphism*, is introduced, which enhances the previously established notion of cognitive prisms.

I. Background

The world as perceived by humans and other intelligent animals is variegated and complex for a variety of reasons. For instance, the human brain includes specialized regions devoted to the facilities of a single sense, (e.g. the olfactory bulb; Shepherd and Greer, 1998).¹ Thanks to this delicate internal topology, the subjective experience of these animals is inherently *multimodal*.

¹ Shepherd and Greer provide an accessible overview of the olfactory bulb; other specialized sensorial regions of the brain include the V1 Visual Cortex; the mathematically interested reader may want to consult (Bressloff & Cowan et. al, 2002) for a formal modeling of this area.

Multimodality is a term used by social theorists and semioticians to describe a medium which incorporates many distinct sub-media². As an example, a film in which subtitles are displayed at the bottom of screen constitutes a medium which includes the sub-media of written text, spoken dialogue, moving imagery, etcetera, which are all simultaneously registered and interpreted by the audience. Another example is in everyday human speech, where tone, inflection, prosody, etc., all combine to form a unified speech act. Oftentimes, one of these sub-media will predominate over the others, which seems to evidence the hypothesis that media observation is a microcosm of the attention economy as a whole; since the various attributes cannot all simultaneously receive full focus, the highly differentiated regions of the brain are in competition with one another, leading to an internalized and evolving *psychic ecosystem*³ in which niche formation, thought migration, and mimetic reproduction occur.

Due to the competing modes of perception available to most vertebrates, these animals must employ (consciously or otherwise) means of *filtering* the information available to them in order to ensure that their perception of the world is meaningful or relevant to themselves. Humans in particular are frequently characterized as *cognitive misers*, meaning that they rely on "cognitive shortcuts" in order to process information. There is a long-standing philosophical tradition in the west⁴ of emphasizing human reason as unique and differentiated from the traits of other animals. It is then natural to accept that the miserliness of humans and the scarcity of mental resources in a relatively competitive attention economy would lead to simplified mental representations of the world which balance these resources with the complexity of the world. In fact, these mental representations are commonly referred to as **schemata** (*singular*: schema). Some common examples of schemata are stereotypes, heuristics, and worldviews.

In the Buddhist tradition of Abhidhamma⁵, there is a clear distinction between the process (paññatti) of thinking, and the contents (dhammâ) of the thought act itself. Whereas the paññatti is experienced by the thinker, (s)he does not and cannot experience the thought content itself because it is phenomenologically inert, and more importantly, it contains naked *value* and *meaning*⁶ divorced from the concrete reality of direct experience. Frýba⁷ likens such raw *atthâ* to religious dogma; when abstracted from the core contents of direct reality, *atthâ* becomes a sort of "moral code" which is accepted without any requisite proof. Since religion facilitates the mass-scale manufacturing of *atthâ*⁸, it is evident that the purpose of schemata is not merely *economical*, but can be *moral* as well,

2 More precisely, (Kress and Van Leeuwen, 2001) define it as "the use of several semiotic modes in the design of a semiotic product or event." The definition of a semiotic mode is heavily debated; see (Castaldi, 2024) for recent discussions.

3 Multiple therapies founded in mystical tradition are rooted in the proper balance of this "psychic ecosystem"; (Frýba, 2002) on the one hand draws from Abhidhamma; more recently (Gliksberg, 2025) explored this conception in the framework of a Kabbalah-based practice.

4 This argument dates back at least to Plato (ca. 380 BCE), who divided the human soul into three components: reason (λογιστικόν), spirit (θυμοειδής), and appetite (ἐπιθυμητικόν), and claims reason shall rule the others (Plato, 1992/380 BCE, 442c, p. 116). Aristotle later became its most influential expositor. The question of how to demarcate humanity was answered most sardonically by Diogenes, who, upon hearing of the definition of humans as "featherless bipeds," objected by bringing a plucked chicken into Plato's Academy and proclaiming, "Behold! Plato's man!" (Diogenes Laertius, 1925/3rd c. CE, p. 63). We do not take up the task of identifying the essential properties of humans here, but defer instead to Heyes (2019) for a recent theory pertaining to cognition.

5 Frýba, p. 4

6 The term *atthâ* is used to encompass this "meaning-value" concept.

7 Ibid., p. 8

8 The unquestionable adoption of a moral artifact (i.e., propaganda) as seen not only in religious people but in all dogmatic thinkers, is reminiscent of a Marcel Duchamp *readymade*.

and the formation of schemata may be more-or-less idiosyncratic.⁹ The schemata are therefore customizable, but in a healthy person they are constrained by agreement with the known facts.¹⁰

Humans usually desire to hold "true" beliefs. The process of evolution which has produced complex brains seen in vertebrates demands consistent strategies for survival and reproduction. Survival does not occur in any organism which is completely desynchronized from objective reality¹¹, and sexual reproduction cannot occur unless there exists both the appropriate sexual organs *and* the *emotional* and *libidinal* synchronization required for arousal and climax.

However, in spite of this, people appear universally to hold erroneous beliefs. We are easily fooled by optical illusions, rely on flawed methodology to reach conclusions, and our thinking is laden with cognitive biases which require deliberate training to overcome. Our mental models cannot perfectly represent the world, for at least two reasons. Firstly, there are *transcription errors*, in which our perception is not faithfully encoded by our psyche; secondly, we do not merely attempt to mentally recreate the world as-is, but constantly attempt to transgress the boundaries of what is possible via our *imagination*. Thus, there are at least two types of cognitive distortions: mechanical, and creative.

II. On the Construct-Object Theory of Flynn

According to Kyle Flynn, an Oregonian financial consultant, markets analyst, and computer programmer, creative cognitive distortions are a form of *strategic conjugation*. He identified a "fivefold issue"¹², which I shall call here the *creative quandary*. The creative quandary results from one of five reasons; chief among them are *idea incompleteness* and *pragmatic insufficiency*. Idea incompleteness occurs when the desire for cogency exceeds the skill or energy level of the practitioner. In order to complete a difficult idea, one must undergo a regimen of strenuous mental exercise, and in order to develop pragmatic sufficiency, one must build the appropriate cognitive and agentive infrastructure through a series of low-stakes "investments." The building of infrastructure, the attainment of creative fitness, etc., all function as high-level goals which refine the strategic process of goal formation and attainment itself.

Flynn¹³ prescribes a system of tabulation and recording of one's practical achievements as the output of all constructive endeavors. This document serves as an account of all the technical¹⁴ and practical mastery one has acquired, and thus as a document of biotechnics¹⁵. The measurement of mastery results in a process of psychological and spiritual refinement. This creates a feedback loop in which one is able to mitigate chronic deficiency and instability, by reinforcing the pragmatic interaction between the constructive and objective domains. The practitioner of any marketable skill, be it language or time management, operates within a dynamical system where "true goals¹⁶" are discovered and attempted. Each attempt is a miniature experiment, and awareness of its results allows for the formulation of improved strategies. By systematically enhancing one's strategies, via the refinement of schemata such as heuristics, the truthfulness of positive status is reified.

9 Flynn, 2019

10 Further, even empathy can come into play as a restriction when consciously formulating an ethical schema. A future work might be useful for investigating other motives for schematization, and the ways in which they inhibit the process of schematizing.

11 It has long been established (Srinivasan and Padmavati, 1997) that Schizophrenic individuals (particularly males) have significantly fewer children than healthy controls.

12 Flynn, p. 1

13 Ibid., p. 3

14 In the sense of (Buchanan, 2025)

15 Ibid. pp. 8-10 Meaning: "way of living"

16 Flynn, p. 2

The vehicle for realizing increasingly higher-level awareness is what Flynn calls a "construct-object."¹⁷ It is defined, verbatim, as "a psychological tool for interaction with the apparent universe." Flynn divides the construct-object into four distinct branches: *imitative*, *innovative*, *immersive*, and *intuitive*. The first two are of primary importance to us, because they constitute a single dimension, and their relationship to each other is most clear.¹⁸ Theories of psychological type characterize people according to which CO dominates each qualitative dimension. These models have largely been replaced in the last thirty years with trait-based theories, which supposedly avoid stereotyping people into a single role. However, when we compare a trait-based theory like Big 5 to a type-based theory like MBTI, it is clear that they are not much different; intuitiveness roughly corresponds to openness to experience; conscientiousness corresponds to judgment; and the rest is roughly the same. However, they do have the advantage of differentiating between small and large tendencies in one direction.

§ Iib Clinical Speculation: The Rôle of Schematic Imitation-Innovation

It is important to be cautious when speculating upon the relationship between COs and mental illness. Since CO was not envisaged as a clinical theory, a great deal of interpretation and some creative liberties are required in order to make these connections. I shall emphasize that *schematic* innovation and imitation are markedly different from their *pragmatic* versions. Pragmatic imitation may perhaps be higher in OCPD and narcissist populations and deficient in schizotypal, bipolar, and gender-variant persons. In many societies, pragmatic imitation is seen as "healthy" whereas innovation is inherently risky.

The mechanical distortions of cognition are largely failures of the imitative faculties of the psyche, and shall be regarded as negative symptoms of an unspecified neurosis or psychosis, and are related to memory or attention deficits; meanwhile, the creative distortions, introduced by the imagination, are positive symptoms, and manifest themselves in the full-blown psychotic person as hallucinations. In a healthy individual, the mechanical failures are relegated to the least relevant details most of the time, whereas the creative "failures" are typically not even present, but instead all creativity is used up by what Flynn might call the rhetorical aspects of speech, including references to mythology, inside jokes, and puns.¹⁹ Failures of the first type may be related to progressive conditions such as Alzheimer's, whereas failures of the latter type may be related to Autism or Schizophrenia.

III. Ontological Status of Construct-Objects

Having summarized construct-objects, I shall proceed to a discussion of their ontological aspects. On one hand, COs seem to be a form of schemata themselves; in this view, they are simply tools of the psyche, and conscious ones at that.

I would like to argue that CO pairs²⁰ like imitation-imagination, which form continuous dimensions, represent *objective modalities* of being, and so in this way are not merely *mental constructs*, but quasi-objective ones. We must consider that sensory experiences are not merely

17 The hyphenation is my own; the original manuscript reads as "construct object." We will follow Flynn and abbreviate this by CO.

18 Flynn's original typology is admittedly rather crude, and in principle it can and should be modified infinitely, in accordance with the infinitude of possible mental landscapes.

19 These jokes and references may be considered "cringeworthy" or painfully unfunny, but whether that is a failure in the sense of distortion is up for debate.

20 I shall use the terms "CO Pair" and "CO Dipole" interchangeably

subjective or objective, but also *transjective*.²¹ For instance, the so-called "mechanical senses" of hearing and seeing rely on a process known as *transduction*, in which waves (optical or audial²²) are converted into sensation by, for example, a retina. Sight and sound both admit a spectrum of frequencies, so that values lying within a specific interval, and only those values, are available to our consciousness.²³ Mathematically, these intervals are little more than a dimension along which a modality (color or pitch) is received. These dimensions are not entirely unlike the dimensions of dipolar COs. If we treat each dipolar CO as a one-dimensional vector space (*VS*), then the combination of all COs would then be a higher-dimensional *VS*. We could then posit that transduction is a *VS isomorphism*. According to (Wertheimer, 2010), *isomorphism* is a concept from Gestalt psychology in which the subjective experience of a neurological stimulus faithfully correspond to the Gestalt aspects of the stimulus itself.

§ IIIb Further Speculation

Perhaps there is an underlying transjective potential latent in all "things," be them in the mind or in actuality. This transjective potential could lie on a gradient, like color, and *objective-subjective* could form a construct-object dipole; then, it seems plausible to suggest that there is another dipole: *stimulative-cognitive*. We would then have an ontological *VS isomorphism* between the two pairs, and thus these two halves of the universe are both ontologically and epistemologically real. The cognitive distortions, i.e. the deviance of mental models from "reality," constitute *diffeomorphisms*

$$\mathbf{P}: \mathbf{O} \rightarrow \mathbf{E}$$

which we might call "perceptomorphisms," from the space **O** (the *ontic* space) to the space **E** (the *epistemic* space). When two perceptomorphisms overlap on large intersections, we say that they have a high-degree of *mutual intelligibility*. If a collection of agents **A** is such that the mutual intelligibility of some construct-object class **C** is high, we say that **A** *exhibits*²⁴ *consilience* on **C**.

In practice, it is extremely difficult to verify whether a collection of agents exhibit consilience on a fact **F**, for suppose that two agents **A** and **B** were to explain their understanding of the fact **F** in a common language. This already invites difficulties, as agents do never really speak from a common language, but rather distinct *idiolects*, which are effectively personalized dialects of the language. We can never be sure whether the agreement between the agents is identical only in sign, or in the signified itself. However, some branches of knowledge, such as mathematics, seem to show a markedly greater deal of consilience than the rest. We will assume that if the agents are consilient on many facts at the epistemic level, then they agree on a non-negligible subset of the ontic commitments of these facts.²⁵

21 An exact source alludes me, but this is a concept expounded upon by John Vervaeke, though he is not the inventor of this term.

22 Audio waves are "*transverse waves*."

23 It is unsure whether values outside these ranges can be subconsciously "perceived," but there does not seem to be any evidence of this; *perception* seems to lie exclusively within the consciousness.

24 The term "exhibit" is to be used in the sense of museums; see (Buchanan, 2024).

25 By this, I mean that if many of the meta-tags (Buchanan, 2024) and stereotypes referenced by two agents **A** and **B** seem to correspond, then it can be inferred that the agents make reference to similar museums. Recall that a cognitive prism is a three-dimensional construct with dimensions **V**, **R**, **E**, which are respectively, the *visits* of a museum, its number of *relata*, and its *exhibits*. By hypothesis, I am assuming that two agents with measurably similar cognitive prisms agree not only on the epistemic concerns, but ontological ones as well. However, this need not always be the case; it may be that prism **I** in **A**'s mind corresponds to a prism **J** in **B**'s mind which cannot be pulled back to (i.e., are not projections of) common museums. This is the classic case of "is my red really your blue?" It seems that biological disparities, in e.g. the eye, would seem to mandate this possibility; however, an agent with more cones in their eyes than another can be argued to have "visited" the visual modalities of a museum more times than the other, and therefore would have a more balanced prism. Therefore, animals with greater specializations in certain area of the brain may be viewing these

IV. Future Work

A detailed comparison of Flynn's theory with the *personal construct theory* of George Kelly is warranted. The theories are not entirely unlike one another; Kelly sees individuals as scientists who formulate *personal constructs* of the world around them, and revise these constructs according to new data. More explication would greatly benefit this paper by grounding construct-objects in a larger class of construct theories.

Formal mathematical modeling, e.g. using the *free energy principle* and active inference, would also bolster the credibility of our ideas, and would make room for computational, rather than interpretative, semiotics. However, the theory as it stands is ill-suited for a literal instantiation; a toy model, however, is possible.

Lastly, a careful reading of the clinical literature would allow for more realistic implementations of both the theory of museums, and the theory of construct-objects. Specifically, the relationship between Freud's topography of the psyche, autism, and personal disorders as they relate to perceptomorphic imbalances, would open the door for a practical, down-to-Earth application of these theories. As of now, they remain purely speculative, and we have focused on building the conceptual architecture (*knowledge engineering*) for analyzing the world in a new way. Cross-pollination with scholars in adjacent areas, such as psychoanalysis, active inference, and semiotics, will be necessary in order for the maturity of Museum Theory.

aspects of reality as is, with less cognitive distortion. However, the organism does not have a greater grasp on reality as a whole, for the number of visits to these exhibits is heavily biased compared with other exhibits, so the perceptomorphism is only locally faithful.

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